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The transcriptional landscape of basal-like subtype breast cancer in humans: CCT5.

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Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies to define the transcriptional landscape of basal-like subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here differential expression of CCT5 in the subtype of human breast cancer known as basal-like.

1 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from
2 patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression
3 analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of basal-like subtype breast
4 cancer.

4 **Methods**

5 We utilized microarray datasets GSE45827 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene
6 expression analysis of basal-like subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based
7 computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE45827 was generated using
8 [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=11$ normal breast
9 tissues (control) and $n=41$ basal-like subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis
10 was performed using GPL570. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array
11 [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=14$ primary breast
12 tumors of basal-like subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform
13 GPL6244. We used an R-based bioinformatic tool to perform whole transcriptome co-regulation studies
14 across multiple tissues (SEEK [6]). We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor
15 gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$
16 basal subtype patients, in $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in
17 $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (7).

13 **Rationale**

14 Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

15 **Results**

16 We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene
17 expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose
18 expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the basal-like subtype of human
19 breast cancer.

- 19 1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal-like subtype.

20 $n=11$ normal breast tissues (human)

21 $n=41$ primary tumors (breast; human; basal-like)

22 ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
23 208696_at	5.66E-14	-10.121922	21.398713	-1.9292453	CCT5	1555/ 29873	94.8

24 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and basal-like breast
25 tumors, we discovered differential expression of chaperonin containing TCP1 subunit 5, encoded by CCT5
26 (located at 5p15.2) in basal-like breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of CCT5 changed
27 more than 94% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose
28 expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change
indicating increased quantity of CCT5 messenger RNA in basal-like subtype tumors, demonstrating
up-regulation of CCT5 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to basal-like breast
cancer.

2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal-like subtype

$n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=14$ primary tumors (breast; human; basal-like)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8104449	1.03E-12	-9.4331274	18.759908	-1.3925513	CCT5	376/33297	98.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and basal-like breast tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CCT5 in basal-like breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The expression of CCT5 here changed more than 98% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CCT5 messenger RNA in basal-like subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CCT5 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to basal-like breast cancer.

Thus, CCT5 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the basal-like breast cancer subtype in humans.

In breast cancer as in any solid tumor, the function of the gene identified by whole transcriptome differential gene expression cannot be assumed to be the same as in non-transformed tissues. Thus, to identify gene products likely to interact with and/or be relevant to the differentially expressed genes function in the transformed tissue, we performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation studies using SEEK, an R-based computational tool that blindly and quantitatively identifies co-expression across the genome using a clustering method rather than integration-based differential gene expression methodology (6). This second whole transcriptome technology identified BRIX1, NSUN2, CCT6A, TRIP13, SNRPD1 as the five genes across the transcriptome most closely co-regulated with CCT5 in the transformed human breast (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed human breast: CCT5.

1 Finally, we measured the influence of CCT5 tumor gene expression on overall survival in humans
 2 with breast cancer (**Figure 2**) (7).

19 **Fig. 2: Relationship between CCT5 tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.**
 20 Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A
 21 subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and
 22 patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

23 **Discussion**

24 We describe here CCT5 as a component gene product of the basal-like subtype in human breast
 25 cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor
 26 evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.

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